

Powder epoxy based composites for structural strengthening applications

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Outline

- ❑ Background
- ❑ Powder epoxies
- ❑ Methodology: Sample preparation and tests
- ❑ Results and discussion
- ❑ Conclusions and future work

Background – FRP str.

- ❑ Strengthening or repairing of concrete structures
- ❑ Sheet/plates or near surface mounted bars (NSM)
- ❑ Glass, aramid or carbon fibre reinforcements
- ❑ Improved flexural, shear, axial or combined loads performance

Background – FRP str.

- ❑ Easy and quick application
- ❑ Significantly improved performance
- ❑ Extended service life
- ❑ Corrosion resistance
- ❑ Flexibility and tailorability

- ❑ Rely on bond quality
- ❑ Poor performance at extreme conditions (temperature, salinity, freeze-thaw cycle)
- ❑ Cost

Powder epoxies

- ❑ Melt – cure separation
- ❑ Ability of co-curing
- ❑ Low viscosity
- ❑ Long shelf life
- ❑ Less exotherm during curing
- ❑ Hand layup, prepreg, tape

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The objective of this work is to investigate the potential of powder epoxy based composites in structural strengthening applications.

CFRP Plate production

Unidirectional stitched CF fabric
SAERTEX, 298 g/m²

Powder Epoxy
PE6405, 1220 kg/m³

Manual layup
4 layers

Hot press
1h @120°C, 1 bar

Uncured CFRP plates

Concrete blocks

Wet concrete casting

Curing
28 days

Surface roughing with needle gun

Surface
Prep.

Final samples

Curing

Temp. monitoring

Press configuration

Thermocouple positioning

Curing model

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{(k_1 + k_2 + k_3 \alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n}{1 + \exp[C(\alpha - \alpha_c(T))]}$$

$$k_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{RT}\right)$$

Parameter (Unit)	Value	Parameter (Unit)	Value
A_1 (s ⁻¹)	4.073×10^{-4}	m	1.24
E_1 (J/mol)	12,006	n	1.8
A_2 (s ⁻¹)	10.112×10^{-9}	C	50
E_2 (J/mol)	111,792	$\alpha_c(T)$	$0.006T - 1.748$
A_3 (s ⁻¹)	$1,636 \times 10^{13}$	H_T (J/g)	184
E_3 (J/mol)	131,240	R (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	8.3144626

Degree of cure (DoC) model

Model parameters

Pull off tests

Single shear
pull off tests

CFRP/GFRP strips cured
on concrete blocks

Pull off tests

Test schematic

Pull off tests

$$P_u = 0.427 \beta_p \beta_L b_p L_e \sqrt{f'_c}$$

$$L_e = \sqrt{\frac{E_p t_p}{\sqrt{f'_c}}}$$

$$\beta_p = \sqrt{\frac{2 - b_p/b_c}{1 + b_p/b_c}}$$

$$\beta_L = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } L \geq L_e \\ \sin \frac{\pi L}{2L_e} & \text{if } L \leq L_e \end{cases}$$

P_u : bond strength [N]

β_L : effective length factor

β_p : width factor

L : total bonded length [mm]

L_e : effective length [mm]

b_p : plate width [mm]

b_c : concrete width [mm]

f'_c : concrete cylinder compressive strength [MPa]

E_p : FRP plate modulus [MPa]

t_p : plate thickness [mm]

Curing predictions

Thermocouple data

DoC predictions by the model

Cured FRP strips

Cured GFRP strips

Cured CFRP strips

Cured FRP strips

Increased plate width

Profile of ridges on concrete surface

Air voids

Wet peel ply

Water droplets

Pull off tests results

Curing cycle	Specimen ID	$P_{u,theor}$ [kN]	$P_{u,exp}$ [kN]	$\frac{P_{u,exp}}{P_{u,theor}}$	u_{max} [mm]	Failure mode
T_220_1	B4-G3	10.1	4.58	0.45	2.41	A-CI, A
T_220_4	B5-G4	9.7	2.08	0.22	0.59	A-CI, A
	B6-G5	10.4	7.96	0.77	3.37	A-CI, C
T_260_4	B7-G6	9.2	10.3	1.12	5.99	A-CI, C
	B8-G7	8.7	7.96	0.91	4.37	A-CI
T_220_7	B12-G8	10.3	7.40	0.72	3.12	A-CI, A, C
	B11-G9	9.2	7.26	0.79	4.74	A-CI, A, C
	B9-C1	27.1	14.6	0.54	3.65	C
	B10-C2	27.6	12.3	0.45	3.25	A-CI, C, V
	B13-C3	26.9	16.7	0.62	8.43	C
	B14-C5	29.4	9.68	0.33	2.34	C
	B15-C7	30.9	5.41	0.18	1.71	A-CI, A
	B16-C8	28.1	12.6	0.45	3.16	A-CI, C, V

Key: C – failure in concrete, A-CI: adhesive concrete interface, V: presence of voids A: adhesive failure

Pull off test results

Pull off test results

Failure load vs. DoC predictions

Conclusions

- The potential of powder epoxy in structural strengthening applications
- Design flexibility: Uncured CFRP plates and GFRP semipregs
- Challenges in maintaining precise temperature control during curing
- Non-uniform DoC profile
- Adequately cured regions show good adhesion performance
- Promising results in terms of both FRP and adhesion
- Improved temperature control and curing techniques required for uniform curing

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Thank you

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22